

Aphasia

As psycholinguistics emphasizes, communication is the most powerful tool in human life and a consequence of complex processes in the brain. Thus, through communication individuals can engage in meaningful interaction and obtain a meaningful life experience. Indeed, speech and language increase the productivity of communication. There are significant brain regions such as the arcuate fasciculus, Broca's area, superior temporal gyrus, angular gyrus, supramarginal gyrus, Wernick's area, middle temporal gyrus, Heschl's gyrus in the left hemisphere that mainly associate with the individuals' language functions (Hallowell, 2017). Therefore, damage to these brain regions leads to the acquisition of certain neurogenic language disorders, which can be denoted as aphasia. The primary goal of this study is to investigate the causes, symptoms, and prevalence of aphasia, as well as to critically evaluate appropriate aphasia treatment approaches based on available research evidence.

According to the National Aphasia Association, stroke is the most common cause of aphasia, with 35% to 40% of stroke patients diagnosed with aphasia. Concomitantly, traumatic brain injuries, brain tumors, brain infections, and certain progressive neurological diseases have also been revealed as causes of aphasia (Bohra et al., 2015). According to National Institute on Deafness and Other Communication Disorders (2015) estimates, one million individuals are living with aphasia in the United States. It is also noted that post-stroke aphasia is more common in adults than in the younger generation. Indeed, aphasia is one of the most devastating disorders caused by a lack of access to communicative activities.

Aphasia has become a more life-challenging disorder due to the impairment of speech and language expression and comprehension. Due to the level of communication, aphasia is divided into fluent and nonfluent forms (Albert, 1988). Broca's aphasia, Wernicke's aphasia, conduction aphasia, anomic aphasia, transcortical motor aphasia, transcortical sensory

aphasia, and, later, global aphasia (Marshall, 2010). Based on the severity of the impairment in these particular areas, determine the degree of an individual's fluency, speech production, and comprehension.

Lesion of Broca's area, which is located in the inferior posterior frontal lobe, causes Broca's aphasia. This type of aphasia can be denoted as "nonfluent aphasia" due to the severe impairment of speech production. It is further denoted, that the inability to combine linguistic elements such as adverbs and adjectives and the grammatical functions of sentences is being omitted due to this condition. Bohra et al. (2015) discovered that 28.3% of poststroke aphasia patients had Broca's aphasia based on MRI and CT scan results. Wernicke's aphasia is another common type of aphasia that predates Broca's aphasia. Individuals with this condition are fluent but have severe auditory comprehension impairments. Thus, individuals were not able to make associations between different words and their meanings due to the lesion in Wernicke's area (Marshall, 2010). Therefore, no one can understand what they are saying. Hence, clinicians also emphasize this condition as "jargon aphasia. Conduction aphasia is caused by a lesion of an individual's arcuate fasciculus, which causes an association between the anterior and posterior language centers (Beaumont, 2008). According to clinical observations, individuals with this condition have the capacity to understand speech and writing clearly and normally. However, due to specific brain region impairment, even if the individual understands the language and written material, he or she is unable to repeat it or tell others where it came from.

Beaumont (2008) defines anomia as an impairment of the angular gyrus and middle posterior temporal lobe. When writing, people with this condition may have difficulty comprehending the words and finding the correct words (Albert, 1988). It is also noted that anomia patients frequently use incorrect nouns when communicating with one another.

According to the study, a lesion of the frontal association cortex causes transcortical motor aphasia. As a result, people with this condition are completely illiterate and unable to write. Despite the predominant impairment in speech, the ability to repeat language has not been compromised (Holland et al., 2016). Hence, clinicians denote this condition as echolalic aphasia (Albert, 1988).

Additionally, transcortical sensory aphasia is a consequence of a lesion in the peri-sylvian association cortex (Beaumont, 2008). According to clinical observations, impairment of auditory comprehension is the main symptom of this condition. It is also stated that despite poor reading comprehension, the ability to read is normal. A large lesion of the anterior and posterior white matter regions responsible for language is also affected, resulting in a severe type of aphasia known as global aphasia (Albert, 1988).

Based on measurable logistic impairments related to aphasia such as lexical retrieval, sentence production, and the ability to produce suitable morphology and utility of grammatical forms, speech-language therapists are conducting several psycholinguistic assessments such as the Schuell short examination, the Boston Diagnostic Aphasia Examination, and the Halstead-Wepman Aphasia Screening Test to assess the patient's level of aphasia and determine the suitable treatment process (Beaumont, 2008). Thus, there are various therapies such as deblocking therapy, visual communication therapy, syntax stimulation therapy, verb network strengthening therapy (Thompson et al., 2013), melodic intonation therapy, and script therapy that facilitate the recovery of adequate communication ability (Beaumont, 2008).

Among them, verb network strengthening and script therapy can be denoted as multi-model training methods that facilitate the development of functional sentence production and are emphasized as the most feasible methods for individuals who are having moderate to severe

aphasia (Edmonds, 2016). In fact verb network strengthening treatment is an impairment-specific approach that has emerged to address the deficit of lexical retrieval and enhance the semantic representation of verbs. Script therapy is a social functional approach that has focused on aphasia patients' communicational environment and daily participation in life activities (Yacono & Balasubramanian, 2018). Whereas the verb strengthening treatment method mainly focuses on the impairment of language structure and improving the relevant weaker areas. Edmonds and Bobb (2010) conducted research and discovered that verb strengthening treatment is more appropriate for moderate to severe aphasia because it covers a wide range of linguistic areas such as verb production, naming, sentence production, and word retrieval. Concomitantly, this method concerns the language components as building blocks that facilitate communication abilities. Therefore in this treatment method patient is given a particular agent and target verb and requests to build connections and recall the connections. In addition, the therapist asks questions using who, what, why, and when to establish a strong network with specific agents and verbs (Thompson et al., 2013). According to empirical evidence, through the encouragement of response generalization towards the lexical items and stimulus generalization towards the various linguistic tasks in this treatment method, aphasia patients have shown substantial improvement in their sentence production after analyzing the results of Northwestern verb production battery assessment (Thompson & Shapiro, 2005).

As well as script therapy guides for identifying and responding to everyday conversations using script training. These scripts have been documented in three phases, and at the beginning, the speech-language pathologist read the script in front of the patient loudly. In the second round, the clinician let the patient repeat each phrase and sentence with little support from the clinician. In the third stage, the clinician shows only the cue card and lets the patient read the sentence repeatedly (Yacono & Balasubramanian, 2018). In fact, scripts

aid in understanding, remembering, and retrieving the several important steps of daily routine. According to clinical studies, script training is conducted in terms of a phrase hierarchy and allows patients to read and repeat the given phrase. Thus, once the given script is mastered, the generalization phase will be executed, and the ultimate goal of this method is to enhance the patient's social functional communication (Youmans et al., 2005). According to empirical evidence, script therapy has been shown to be more effective for individuals who have agrammatic Broca's aphasia. Aphasia patients have recently been given the option of using computerized scripts, which provide virtual therapists and patient training. As the clinical studies emphasize, most of the aphasia patients' sentences have become short and single, and grammatical components tend to be omitted or absent (Marshall, 2010). In fact, aphasia treatments aid in reconnecting patients with their family members and negotiating with normal life. One of the studies, which was done by monitoring two patients with Broca's aphasia and transcortical motor aphasia, showed different progressive levels after engaging in script therapy. Concurrently, a patient with Broca's aphasia had an accuracy level of 87.5%, and a patient with transcortical motor aphasia had an accuracy level of 63.5% for script therapy post-treatment (Rhodes & Isaki, 2018).

According to field experts' opinions, an aphasia patient's improvement level is determined by the level of severity and the patient's characteristics. Further, the level of communication depends on the patient's ability to produce short or complex sentences (Yacono & Balasubramanian, 2018). According to the limitations of aphasia treatments, clinicians have identified patients' fatigue during speech and language therapy sessions. There was a study done by collecting speech-language pathologists' feedbacks through an online survey that indicated that out of 312 sample of 312 clinicians, 80% observed the patients' fatigue during their therapy sessions, 78% observed the physical signs within their patients, and 97% reported that their performance declined during their sessions (Riley,

2017). When analyzing the empirical evidence, most of the researchers have used small samples in their research, and if they had used larger samples in their research, it would have been highly effective to generalize the most suitable treatment for aphasia and to abstract the limitations of other treatment methods that are being used for aphasia. Since there is a little empirical evidence for the medical follow-ups during the language therapy, it's really important to investigate this area as well. Additionally, the patient's level of motivation, personality characteristics, and level of education are other crucial areas that need to be broadly studied in the future. Indeed, aphasia is a language disorder that is directly affects an individual's quality of life, and speech-language pathologists' main goal is to reconstruct their communication abilities to manage their lives.

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